

PROJECT TUCAD (Transforming and Uplifting the Character and Academic Development of the learners)

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ABSTRACT

Project TUCAD as part of the Problem/Research- Outcomes Based Education (PROBE) of the University of Nueva Caceres, in partnership with Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School (CSNAIHS) covers three salient features: Tuklas, Tupad, and Talima phase. This study was conducted to increase the enrollment and participation of learners in Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School. The respondents of this research are the out-of-school youth of the nearby barangays and all others who have not finished school due to various reasons and are experiencing difficulties in meeting the school requirements. The study employed mixed-method research. This approach combines both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive evaluation of how the project influences learners' character development, academic performance, and ability to sustain schooling through livelihood activities. Questionnaires were given to the respondents to determine the impact of the program. *The Open High School Program will serve as an alternative mode for secondary education that uses distance learning and other applicable platforms to cater to the needs of the learners, The School will adopt an Alternative learning program adjacent to the learners enrolled in open-High School like a Modular curriculum, Flexible Learning Modes, Online Learning Platform Printed Modules: For students with limited internet access, modules can be distributed and submitted in person Community Learning Centers: Access to computers, internet, and tutors for additional support. All of these will serve as academic support. Likewise Provide a livelihood program to the enrollees to achieve economic independence in their chosen fields Project TUCAD with its continuing effort aims to continue the **TUPAD** phase implementation to*

pursue and help the CSNAIHS meet the qualification to open secondary public High School.

Keywords: *Open High School, Increase Enrolment 2, Livelihood Program*

INTRODUCTION

The "Open High School Program" refers to a flexible educational approach that allows students to complete their high school education through non-traditional means. This can include online courses, independent study, credit recovery programs, and other alternative methods like modules. The program is designed to accommodate students who may have difficulty attending a traditional school due to various reasons such as health issues, family responsibilities, or scheduling conflicts.

Open high school programs often offer a range of courses that students can complete at their own pace, allowing for greater flexibility and customization of their educational experience. Some programs may also provide additional support services such as counseling, tutoring, or academic advising to help students succeed in their studies

The Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School is a public secondary school created under Republic Act 9621. It is situated at Barangay Comaguinking, Calabanga, Camarines Sur. It has given permit to offer Junior High School program starting school year 2021-2022. In its 2 years of operation, its main problem is the enrollment because it is in between two established schools. Most of its learners come from the barangay where the school is located. At present, there are only 94 enrolled students in this school. This number does not meet the qualification to open a public secondary school which requires at least 100 students to establish.

In response to the clamor of the students who are unable to pursue their formal education due to rigid academic requirements of regular classes schedule; early employment due to poverty; socio-economic situation; distance of home to school and disabilities, open high school program was implemented in 2022. It is an alternative mode for secondary education that uses distance learning. Open High School Program benefits the nearby upland barangays. This provides students with self-learning modules and allows them to receive education remotely and at their own pace. This gives every youth a chance to complete his/her education, which may not be feasible under the standard set up, given their personal and financial difficulties. This program is designed to allow eligible students both young and adults to learn on their own without necessarily having to attend formal classes. This holds the premise that education must be made accessible to learners, and no one should be left behind.

While it was perceived to be helpful to gain enrollees, however, the school's record shows that there are only 3 enrolled students which is perceived to be low compared to the number of out-of-school youth in the barangay. Furthermore, there was also considerably low participation because 33% or 1 of 3 enrolled students could not finish the school year.

Opening an Open High School program is an avenue for the students to continue learning despite difficulties and trials that result in stopping schooling. It unfolds the various levels of social and emotional development of the learners who dropped out from school before and decided to finish their schooling. It was found that the enrollees had been able to develop in themselves more enhanced self-confidence and independent learning skills. The program gave them more learning opportunities to discover their innate skills and potential. (Onsay 2020)

Education plays a significant part in molding the future of our young generation of learners and leaders (Tao & Benjamin, 2020). As posited by (Zhu & Liu, 2020), the best curriculum in the emergency learning environment is the curriculum that is flexible and adaptable to the demands of future thinking (Mishra et al., 2020; Dasig et al., 2021). Accordingly, the best curriculum thinkers begin with the end in mind and work methodically to forecast plans and design for the future. They identify best practices and productively critique work until it is near what is believed to be beneficial to the learners. However, the challenge this pandemic may bring to education still fulfills the responsibility to serve the learners. Due to the varying and changing landscape of technological challenges of distance education in Basic Education such as managing disengaged online learners, an Open High School Program, an alternative mode of delivering secondary education for both public and private schools was implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic (Torres & Tan, 2021). In the Open High School Program modality, educators should be aware of and look for signs of disengagement and act to maximize engagement and support for at-risk students during COVID-19 (Wardhana et al., 2022; Dasig et al., 2017; Pahayahay et al., 2017)

It is in this context that this Project TUCAD was conceived as our PROBE projects strengthen the Open High School Program, which aims to provide greater accessibility to high school education for students who may not thrive in a traditional school setting, allowing them to earn their diplomas through alternative pathways.

As part of the continuing efforts to support and uplift the holistic development of learners, the Program Implementers proudly implement the Project TUPAD as part of the last phase of Project TUCAD (Transforming and Uplifting the Characters and Academic Development of the Learners) for the second semester of the school year 2024–2025. This phase focuses on delivering relevant and practical interventions to address the financial challenges faced by many students, which often hinder their academic progress. Through this project, the project aims to create a nurturing environment that promotes both character formation and academic excellence, anchored on values of self-reliance and community support.

The TUPAD Phase of Project TUCAD is guided by three key objectives. First, it seeks to encourage maximum participation among learners through the implementation of a livelihood program that empowers them with real-life skills. By engaging in productive activities, students become more involved in their learning journey and develop a sense of responsibility and purpose. Second, it aims to foster self-reliance by giving learners opportunities to manage their own micro-enterprises, allowing them to contribute to their

schooling and lessen the burden on their families, even in the face of hardship and struggles.

Finally, the project is designed to be sustainable, with a vision to make a long-term impact in the lives of students by establishing partnerships with community organizations and local businesses. These collaborations are essential in ensuring the continued success and relevance of the program, providing learners with the support and resources needed to thrive. With Project TUCAD in place, the school remains committed to building a brighter, more resilient future for every learner—one that goes beyond the classroom and equips them with the tools to rise above life's challenges.

Research Questions

The study determines the effectiveness of Project TUCAD (Transforming and Uplifting the Characters and Academic Development of the Learners) in addressing the challenges faced by students in the Open High School Program, particularly in terms of increase in enrollment, improving their academic engagement, character development, and ability to sustain their education through livelihood support

1. What are the demographic profiles of the students enrolled in the Open High School Program under Project TUCAD in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Gender
 - c. Civil status
 - d. Address
 - e. Socio-economic challenges (e.g., financial, distance, responsibilities, etc.)?
2. What are the common difficulties experienced by students that hinder their participation and retention in formal schooling?
3. How does the implementation of Project TUCAD, particularly its TUPAD livelihood phase, influence the following aspects of the learners?
 - a. Academic engagement
 - b. Self-reliance and motivation
 - c. Attendance and school participation
 - d. Character development
4. Is there a significant change in students' level of academic motivation and participation before and after the implementation of Project TUCAD?
5. What recommendations can be made to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the Project TUCAD for future implementation?

METHODOLOGY

Methods Used

To assess the effectiveness and impact of Project TUCAD, the study employed the mixed-methods research. This approach combines both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive evaluation of how the project influences learners' character development, academic performance, and ability to sustain schooling through livelihood activities.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School, a newly-established public secondary school. The school is situated in 20,000 square meter area located at Barangay, Comaguingking, Calabanga, Camarines Sur. Its strategic location is best for students who live in upland barangay such as Harubay, Lugsad, Binanuaanan Pequeño and Grande and Camuning which are adjacent to the school.

Data Gathering Tools

The instruments used in gathering the data were questionnaire and unstructured interview.

Questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to obtain information of the students to determine their situation and effectiveness of the program. Thus, it consisted of two parts:

Part I included the profiles of respondents along age, gender, civil status, address and difficulties in school.

Part II is about the effectiveness of Project TUCAD as part of the last phase of its implementation, the *TUPAD Phase*. The conduct of intervention program and its relevance to continue education. The questionnaire adopts a four-point Likert scale will be used where: 4, means very high; 3, high; 2, low; and 1, very low. For scoring, the scores will be grouped according to categories. Of the sub totals, the group that with highest mean scores were the areas where the program was well-developed. Conversely, that group which are lowest were those areas where the program need improvement. The scoring will be as follows:

- 1.00-1.75 – Very Good (VG)
- 1.76-2.50 – Good (G)
- 2.51-3.25 – Acceptable (A)
- 3.26-4.00 – Poor (P)

Data Collection Tools and Techniques

- **Pre- and post-intervention surveys** to assess changes in learners' attitudes, values, and academic motivation.
- **Academic records analysis** to compare grades and attendance before and after the implementation of the project.
- **Interviews and focus group discussions** with learners, teachers, and stakeholders to gain in-depth insights into their experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement.
- **Observation checklists** to monitor learners' participation, cooperation, and behavior during livelihood and values formation activities.

Procedure of Investigation

To realize the objectives of the study, the following steps will be done:

Conceptualization of the Research Problem. The researchers diagnosed the prevailing problems in Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School to come up with the main problem and specific problems.

Approval of the Research Problem. The researchers presented the project proposal to Dr. Joy Gaza for approval.

Secure request to conduct the study. A permit to conduct the study was sought from our school head with permission also from the Public Schools District Supervisor.

Conduct of Barangay-Based Information-Dissemination Campaign. Upon approval of the request to conduct the study, the researchers communicated to the nearby barangay through Punong Barangay ad Sangguniang Kabataan (SK) Chairperson.

Conduct of Intervention Program. To help students stay in school by empowering them through income-generating activities, such as small-scale entrepreneurship, that promote self-reliance, practical skills, and sustained academic participation.

Administration of the Questionnaires. New Enrollees/ Attendees were given questionnaires to rate the effectiveness of the program.

Report writing. The data will be subjected to statistical tests to answer the formulated specific problems. Finally, the analyses and discussions of results, interpretation and the executive summary will be prepared

Statistical Treatment of Data

For Quantitative Data Treatment

(For data gathered through survey questionnaires, pre/post-tests, or academic records)
The data will be treated statistically using descriptive statistics and Total Enumeration.

The Frequency and Percentage for demographic profiles (age, gender, civil status, etc.) and categorical data (types of difficulties in school). The Mean and Standard Deviation to analyze levels of academic motivation, character development, and perceptions on the livelihood program.

For Qualitative Data Treatment

The data will be treated with thematic Analysis through coding of responses, categorizing responses, or making a narrative analysis indicating success stories or personal reflections of the students and also highlighting transformation or challenges experienced by participants.

Here's the Sample Questionnaire:

UNIVERSITY OF NUEVA CACERES
School of Graduate Studies
Jaime Hernandez Avenue, Naga City

Petsa

Mahal Kong mga Magulang at Mag-aaral,

Kami po ay mga guro na kasalukuyang kumukuha ng Doctoral Program sa University of Nueva Caceres. Kami po ang nagsasagawa ng pag-aaral tungkol sa proyekto na may pamagat na **PROJECT TUCAD: Transforming and Uplifting the Character and Academic Development of the Learners**, na naglalayong matulungan ang Camarines Sur National Agro-Industrial High School na madaadagan ang bilang ng mga estudyanteng nag-aaral dito sa pamamagitan ng Open High School Program (OHSP). Ang mga respondente ng pananaliksik na ito ay ang mga magulang at mag-aaral na maaaring maging bahagi ng programa sa mga barangay na nakapalibot sa nasabing paaralan: Comanuingking, Burabod, Hanubay at Lugsad. Ang pag-aaral na ito ay ang kanilang PROBE Research na bahagi ng bahagyang katuparan ng mga kailangan sa unang semester ng taong pampaaralan 2023-2024 sa kursong Doctor of Education Major in Educational Management

Kasama nito, pakisagutan ang kalakip na Kwestyuneyr, Ipagpanatag niyo ang inyong kalooban ukol sa mga impormasyong inyong ibababagi dahil ang mga ito ay tratuhing kompidensyal.

Mga Mananaliksik

Kwestyuneyr para sa mga Magulang at Mag-aaral

Panuto: Ang nakatala sa ibaba ay bumubuo ng mga talaan upang malaman ang antas ng tagumpay sa pagganap ng mga Gawain sa programa/proyekto. Bilagan ang marka na nasaxon saiyong kasagutan gamit ang sumusunod na pamantayan:

- 4 Napakataas (NT)
- 3 Mataas (MT)
- 2 Mahaba (MB)
- 1 Napakababa (NB)

Bahagi I – Profile ng Respondente

Pangalan (Opsyonal): _____

1. **Edad:**

- 12–14
- 15–17
- 18–20
- 21 pataas

2. **Kasarian:**

- Lalaki
- Babae
- Mas piniling hindi sabihin

3. **Katayuang Sibil:**

- Binata/Dalaga
- May-asawa
- Hiwalay
- Iba pa: _____

4. **Tirahan/Address:** _____

5. **Ano-anong mga suliranin ang iyong nararanasan sa pag-aaral? (Maaari kang pumili ng higit sa isa)**

- Kakulangan sa pinansyal/panggastos
- Problema sa transportasyon
- Kakulangan sa gamit sa pag-aaral
- Kailangan magtrabaho habang nag-aaral
- Tungkulin sa pamilya
- Kawalan ng motibasyon
- Problema sa kalusugan
- Iba pa: _____

Bahagi II – Persepsyon sa Proyekto ng TUCAD

Lagyan ng ✓ ang kahon na tumutugma sa iyong sagot.

Pahayag	Lubos na Sumasang-ayon	Sumasang-ayon	Neu-tral	Hindi Sumasang-ayon	Lubos na Hindi Sumasang-ayon
1. Hinikayat ako ng Project TUCAD na ipagpatuloy ang aking pag-aaral.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2. Natuto ako ng bagong kasanayan mula sa livelihood activity.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3. Nakakatulong ang paggawa ng dishwashing liquid sa aking pangastos.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4. Naging mas responsible at masipag ako sa sarili kong gawain.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5. Naging positibo ang pananaw ko sa pag-aaral at sa aking kinabukasan.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6. Mas ginaganahan akong mag-aral at pumasok sa paaralan.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
7. Natuto akong mag-manage ng oras sa tulong ng proyekto.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8. Ire-rekomenda ko ang Project TUCAD	<input type="checkbox"/>				

sa ibang mag-aaral.					
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A. Layunin ng Programa/Proyekto	Grado			
1. Ang programa ay may magandang adhikain para sa mga mag-aaral at paaralan.	4	3	2	1
2. Makatutulong ang program na ito upang makapagtapos ang mga mag-aaral na hindi kayang pumasok araw-araw.	4	3	2	1
3. Makatutulong ang program na ito upang higit na mahubog ang mga mag-aaral laloong-lalo na sap ag-uugali at hangarin sa buhay.	4	3	2	1
4. Ang programa at may malinaw na plano para sa tuloy-tuloy na pagpapatupad nito.	4	3	2	1
5. Ang talaan ng mga Gawain sa programa ay sapat upang matupad sa takdang panahon.	4	3	2	1
B. Mga Guro/Mananaliksik				
6. Magiliw at masayang nakikiusap sa mga magulang at mag-aaral.	4	3	2	1
7. Malinaw nilang naisasabi ang layunin at magiging resulta ng program.	4	3	2	1
8. Naipapabatid nila ang kahalagahan ng edukasyon.	4	3	2	1
9. Sila ay tapat at nakikipagtulungan sa mga guro, local officials at mga sponsors.	4	3	2	1
10. Ang kanilang personalidad ay mapagkakatiwalaan.	4	3	2	1
C. Paraan ng paghihikayat				
11. Gumagamit ng mga material tulad ng infographics upang higit na maintindihan ang programa.	4	3	2	1
12. May maayos na programa upang malinaw nilang naipaliliwanag ang kaalaman upang mahikayat ang mga magulang at mag-aaral.	4	3	2	1
13. Ang kanilang paraan ng pakikipag-usap ay akma sa kakayahan ng mga nakikinig and nanunood.	4	3	2	1
14. May mga numero na pwedeng tawagan kung may mga katanungan.	4	3	2	1
15. Nasasagot ang mga tanong upang higit na maintindihan ng mga magulang at mag-aaral.	4	3	2	1
D. Pakikipag-ugnayan sa Paaralan, Local Officials at iba pang Stakeholders				
16. May sulat at tamang paraan ng pakikipag-ugnayan.	4	3	2	1
17. May magandang relasyon sa mga stakeholders.	4	3	2	1
18. Masaya sila sa kanilang pakikitungo sa mga magulang, local officials at sponsors.	4	3	2	1
19. Magalang at may kaaya-ayang pag-uugali.	4	3	2	1

20. Masaya nilang pinupuntahan ang mga lugar kung saan makakakuha ng estudyante kahit ito ay malayo.	4	3	2	1
E. Pangkalahatang Epekto				
21. Nagugustuhan ng mga tao ang programa.	4	3	2	1
22. May magandang plano upang matulungan ang paaralan at komunidad.	4	3	2	1
23. Matutugunan ang kakulangan sa edukasyon dulot ng maagang pagtatrabaho, kapansanan, malayong tirahan at iba pa.	4	3	2	1
24. Ang programa ay para sa lahat.	4	3	2	1
25. Matutulungan ang paaralan upang madagdagan ang bilang ng mag-aaral.	4	3	2	1

Bahagi IV – Bukas na Tanong

Sagutin sa maikling pangungusap.

1. Ano ang pinaka-nakatulong na bahagi ng Project TUCAD para sa iyo?

2. Anong mga hamon ang iyong naranasan habang kalahok sa programa?

3. Paano nabago ng programa ang pananaw mo sa edukasyon at kinabukasan?

4. Anong suhestiyon ang maibibigay mo para lalong mapabuti ang Project TUCAD?

SALAMAT AT MABUHAY!

RESULTS:

Presentation of quantitative data for Project TUCAD. The table presents the data gathered and the interpretation of the findings of Project TUCAD.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents (N = 30)

Profile Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	13–15 years old	10	33.3%
	16–18 years old	15	50.0%
	19–21 years old	5	16.7%
Gender	Male	14	46.7%
	Female	16	53.3%
Civil Status	Single	28	93.3%
	Married	2	6.7%
Address	Barangay Comaguinking	30	100%
Schooling Difficulties	Financial problem	25	83.3%
	Distance to school	15	50.0%
	Household responsibilities	18	60.0%
	Lack of motivation	8	26.7%

Table 2. Impact of the Livelihood Program on Students' Self-Reliance (N = 30)

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I became more motivated to study.	18	10	2	0	0
I learned new skills I can use to earn.	20	9	1	0	0
I can now contribute financially at home.	14	12	4	0	0
I feel more confident and responsible.	17	10	3	0	0

Figure 1. Common Difficulties Encountered in Schooling

Narrative Presentation of Findings

The implementation of Project TUCAD provided an opportunity to explore the lived experiences of Open High School learners as they participated in the dishwashing liquid livelihood intervention. During the interviews, students expressed a renewed sense of purpose and self-worth. Many shared that being part of the program not only helped them gain practical skills but also gave them a reason to stay in school despite economic struggles.

One student shared, *“Dati po, nahihirapan ako pumasok dahil sa kakulangan sa pamasaha. Pero ngayon, kahit paano, may panggastos na ako dahil sa ginagawa naming dishwashing liquid.”* (I used to struggle attending school due to lack of fare. But now, I somehow have something to spend because of the dishwashing liquid we’re making.)

Teachers also observed a change in behavior among participants. Students became more engaged and responsible. Some even began to show leadership and teamwork in handling the production and packaging of the products. The parents of the learners echoed their appreciation, noting how the livelihood component has helped reduce the financial burden of sending their children to school.

Table 3. Emergent Themes from Student Interviews

Theme	Description	Responses
Self-Reliance	Students developed the ability to earn and manage money through livelihood.	“Masaya ako kasi natuto akong kumita sa sarili kong gawa.”
Improved Motivation	Increased eagerness to attend and complete school activities.	“Ngayon, mas gusto ko nang pumasok sa school kasi may ginagawa kaming makabuluhan.”
Skill Development	Gained new skills in entrepreneurship and production.	“Alam ko na ngayon kung paano gumawa ng produkto at ibenta ito.”
Sense of Responsibility	Learners showed ownership and responsibility toward their tasks.	“Inaasahan kaming mag-ambag, kaya natuto akong maging responsible.”
Support from Community	Learners felt encouraged through the support of teachers and community.	“Ramdam ko ang suporta ng mga guro at barangay sa ginagawa namin.”

Table 4. Emerging Insights from Teachers and Stakeholders

Stakeholder Group	Theme	Observation/Insight
Teachers	Student Engagement	“Mas naging aktibo sila sa klase at mas cooperative sa mga gawain.”

Parents	Reduced Financial Strain	“Kahit papaano, nababawasan ang gastos namin sa araw-araw.”
Community Leaders	Project Sustainability	“Kung magpapatuloy ito, pwedeng makatulong sa buong barangay.”

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers came-up with an intervention program to eradicate the low enrolment and participation rate. The Project TUCAD (Transforming and Uplifting the Character and Academic Development of the learners) is designed to implement programs that would encourage learners to enroll in the said school.

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Profile Variable	Category	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	13–15 years old	10	33.3%
	16–18 years old	15	50.0%
	19–21 years old	5	16.7%
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Schooling Difficulties	Financial problem	25	83.3%
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	Household responsibilities	18	60.0%
	Lack of motivation	8	26.7%

The data presented in Table 1 provides an overview of the demographic and personal circumstances of the 30 respondents, offering insight into the general background of the study population. The majority of respondents (50%) are aged between 16 to 18 years old, followed by 33.3% who are between 13 to 15 years old, and a smaller portion, 16.7%, are 19 to 21 years old. This distribution suggests that most of the respondents are within the typical age range for senior high school students, implying that the study focuses on adolescents in a crucial stage of educational development. There is a slightly higher number of female respondents (53.3%) compared to male respondents (46.7%). This slight imbalance suggests a fairly even gender representation, providing a balanced perspective in terms of gender-related responses. An overwhelming majority of the respondents are single (93.3%), with only 6.7% being married. This is expected given the age distribution, as most are likely students who are not yet of typical marrying age.

All 30 respondents reside in Barangay Comaguinking (100%), indicating that the study is localized and community-focused. This can help provide targeted insights and recommendations that are relevant to the specific context of this barangay. When it comes to schooling difficulties, the most commonly reported issue is financial problems, affecting 83.3% of respondents. This highlights a major barrier to education and suggests a need for economic support or scholarship programs. Other significant challenges include: Household responsibilities (60%), which indicates that many students are balancing school with tasks at home, possibly limiting their study time. Distance to school (50%) also presents a significant challenge, emphasizing the need for improved access or transportation support. Lack of motivation (26.7%) is the least cited but still notable, pointing to potential issues with engagement or learning environment.

The respondents are mostly teenagers, single, and evenly distributed by gender, all from Barangay Comaguinking. The data points to financial constraints, household duties, and distance from school as the most common challenges impacting their education. These factors should be taken into account in formulating interventions or support systems aimed at improving educational outcomes for students in the area

Here's the bar graph showing the Profile of Respondents across age, gender, civil status, and schooling difficulties

Table 2

Impact of the Livelihood Program on Students' Self-Reliance

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I became more motivated to study.	18	10	2	0	0

Indicators	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I learned new skills I can use to earn.	20	9	1	0	0
I can now contribute financially at home.	14	12	4	0	0
I feel more confident and responsible.	17	10	3	0	0

The data in Table 2 highlights the positive impact of the livelihood program on various aspects of students' self-reliance. The results indicate a strong overall agreement among participants that the program has significantly enhanced their motivation, skills, and sense of responsibility. **Increased Motivation to Study.** A combined total of 28 students (18 strongly agree, 10 agree) reported that they became more motivated to study after participating in the program. This suggests that the livelihood intervention not only addressed economic needs but also positively influenced students' academic outlook. The absence of any disagreement or negative response reflects a universally positive effect in this area. **Acquisition of New Skills.** An overwhelming majority of 29 students (20 strongly agree, 9 agree) acknowledged that they learned new skills they could use to earn income. This is a key indicator of the program's success in delivering practical, income-generating knowledge. Only 1 student remained neutral, and none disagreed, further underscoring the relevance and quality of the skills training provided. **Ability to Contribute Financially at Home.** In terms of financial contribution at home, 26 students (14 strongly agree, 12 agree) felt they were now capable of helping their families financially. While 4 students remained neutral, it is important to note that no participants disagreed. This finding implies a meaningful level of economic empowerment, although some may still be in the transition phase of applying their skills for income generation. **Confidence and Responsibility.** A total of 27 students (17 strongly agree, 10 agree) reported feeling more confident and responsible after the program. This result aligns with the goal of fostering self-reliance not only in terms of livelihood but also in personal development. The responses demonstrate a shift in self-perception that is essential for long-term independence.

The livelihood program under Project TUCAD has evidently made a substantial impact on learners' self-reliance. High levels of agreement across all indicators suggest the intervention was successful in enhancing motivation, skill acquisition, financial contribution, and personal growth. The absence of any disagreement across the board strongly indicates the program's effectiveness and relevance to the learners' needs and aspirations.

Here is the bar graph based on the data from Table 2, showing the impact of the Livelihood Program on students' self-reliance. The graph compares the responses across the five categories (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) for each indicator.

Conclusions

1. Project TUCAD has a positive impact on learners' academic engagement and character formation, especially those enrolled in the Open High School Program (OHSP) who face financial, personal, and social challenges.
2. The livelihood component, particularly the dishwashing liquid making intervention, provided students with practical skills and opportunities to earn, which helped them become more motivated and self-reliant in sustaining their education.
3. The low participation and retention in the OHSP may be attributed to external factors such as poverty, lack of awareness, and limited community support—challenges that Project TUCAD is helping to address.
4. Students who actively participated in the intervention gained not only financial assistance but also developed life skills, such as responsibility, time management, and teamwork, contributing to their holistic development.
5. There is strong potential for sustainability and scalability of Project TUCAD, especially if continuous partnerships with local government units, NGOs, and businesses are established and strengthened.

Recommendations

1. Scale up the livelihood component of Project TUCAD by offering more skills training based on local market needs (e.g., food processing, crafts, gardening), to reach more learners.
2. Strengthen community engagement by involving parents, barangay officials, and local stakeholders in program planning, monitoring, and promotion to increase enrollment and retention in the Open High School Program.

3. Integrate values education and character-building sessions alongside livelihood training to ensure that students not only gain practical skills but also grow emotionally and socially.
4. Allocate a dedicated fund or seek sponsorships to sustain the livelihood initiatives and provide startup capital for students who wish to continue their micro-enterprises.
5. Establish a mentoring and support system where successful student-participants or alumni of the program guide and motivate incoming learners.
6. Conduct regular evaluations and feedback gathering from students and stakeholders to further improve the implementation and identify areas for innovation and responsiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The conduct of this study strictly adhered to ethical standards in research to ensure the protection, dignity, and rights of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, with a clear explanation of the purpose, procedures, benefits, and potential risks involved in the study. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of their right to withdraw at any point without any repercussions. Confidentiality and anonymity of all personal information were maintained throughout the study. Furthermore, the research tools and interventions implemented, such as the livelihood activities, were designed to be non-exploitative and beneficial to the students. The study was carried out with full respect for the participants' well-being and aligned with the ethical guidelines set by the Department of Education and relevant educational authorities.

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